

Book Review

N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya (ed.). 2015. *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya: The Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya of Khaṇḍadeva with the Sāraprakāśikā Commentary* (Regards sur l'Asie du Sud/South Asian Perspective 4). Pondichéry: Institut Français de Pondichéry. xxi + 664 pp., ISBN 978-81-8470-204-0, ₹1200, €52,00 (Hardcover).

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Prior to the well-known *paṇḍita* N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya (Rāmānuja Tātācārya)'s edition, the *Bhattatantrarahasya* has been edited three times. Cardona (2017: 410) informs us that the most recent edition was published in 1985 with the *Khaṇḍadevabhāvaprakāśa*, a commentary by Sūryanārāyaṇa Śāstrī (Sūryanārāyaṇa Śāstrī 1985).¹ Another edition is Subrahmanya Sastri (1970). In the 1985 edition we find an introduction in English (pp. x–xxi) by K. T. Pandurangī and a long introduction in Sanskrit by Sūryanārāyaṇa Śāstrī where he mentions and criticises A. Subrahmanya Sastri's commentary, and refers (p. lviii) to a still earlier edition, published in 1900.²

The author of the root-text is a well-known pre-modern *mīmāṃsaka*: Khaṇḍadeva Miśra or simply Khaṇḍadeva. In two of the final verses (VII and IX) of the *Prabhāvalī* gloss on the *Bhāṭṭadīpikā*, his pupil Śambhubhaṭṭa affirms that before taking *saṃnyāsa* (asceticism), Khaṇḍadeva lived in Kāśī between 1575 and 1665/1666 (*Vikrama Saṃvat* date 1722). Khaṇḍadeva was a *navya-mīmāṃsaka* author of

¹ Given as follows in the Roman title page: *Khaṇḍa Deva Bhava Prakasa, a Commentary on Mahamhopadhyaya Khandadeva's Bhattarahasya*, Rajahmundry, without any publishers specified (Cardona 2017: 410). Tatacharya refers to Sūryanārāyaṇa Śāstrī's commentary in the *Sāraprakāśikā* (pp. 272–273).

² Which I was not able to access.

the Bhāṭṭa school, as witnessed by his three works on Mīmāṃsā: *Mīmāṃsākaustubha*,³ *Bhāṭṭadīpikā*⁴ and *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya*.

Here I focus on the *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya*, and specifically on the 2015 edition (hereafter BTR). A very detailed review of the *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya* with the *Sāraprakāśikā* commentary, written by the well-known *paṇḍita* N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya (Rāmānuja Tātācārya) has already been published in 2017 by George Cardona (Cardona 2017).

As aptly synthesized in the volume's introduction (pp. ii–iii), the BTR is a philosophical and linguistic work divided into two parts, dealing with the meaning of roots and affixes, and their role in determining the meaning of sentences. The first part of the text introduces the definition of *dharma* according to Jaimini's *Mīmāṃsāsūtra* 1.1.1 (*athāto dharmajijñāsā*) and, while establishing *bhāvanā* (lit. "bringing into being", see Ollett 2013) as the principal meaning of the sentence, it devotes extensive treatment to the meaning of the injunctive suffixes (*vidhipratyaya*). The second part analyses the meanings of nominal case-endings (*vibhakti*) and cases (*kāraka*), discussing several Pāṇinian *sūtras*. In fact, the BTR deals with several linguistic issues presenting them from the point of view of Nyāya, the Pāṇinian grammatical tradition and Mīmāṃsā, but obviously adopting the position of the *bhāṭṭamīmāṃsakas* (Diaconescu 2012: 23–97). Although BTR sometimes deviates from Pāṇinian interpretations, Khaṇḍadeva maintains that there are no grammatical violations by the *mīmāṃsakas*.

This new edition of the BTR is divided into twelve chapters with different coverage: 1. *dharmalakṣaṇavicāraḥ* (pp. 3–17); 2. *vidhivādaḥ* (pp. 19–109); 3. *bhāvanāvādaḥ* (pp. 111–194); 4. *dhātvarthanirūpaṇam* (pp. 195–203); 5. *ākhyātārthanirūpaṇam* (pp. 205–241); 6. *prathamāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 243–275); 7. *dvi-tīyāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 277–378); 8. *ṭṛtīyāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 379–419); 9. *caturthāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 421–466); 10. *pañcamāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 467–521); 11. *ṣaṣṭhāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 523–584); 12. *saptamāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* (pp. 585–640). The volume closes with a series of indexes (*anubandha*, pp. 641–664).⁵

The linguistic work of Khaṇḍadeva should be evaluated for its comprehensive character, and for its logical and systematic arrangement of arguments. This arrangement is similar to those of Kauṇḍabhaṭṭa's *Vaiyākaraṇabhūṣaṇa*, Nāgeśabhaṭṭa's

³ The *Mīmāṃsākaustubha* is a commentary on the sections extending from 1.2 to 3.3 of Jaimini's *Mīmāṃsāsūtra*.

⁴ The *Bhāṭṭadīpikā* is another commentary on Jaimini's *Mīmāṃsāsūtra* from 1.2 to the entire 12 *adhyāya*.

⁵ Cardona (2017, 412) also points out that "the indexes lack references to citations from other texts, which are identified globally in the text". Moreover, even though the indexes provided are fairly comprehensive as to what concerns Pāṇini's *sūtras*, Kātyāyana's *Vārttikas* and Bhartṛhari's *kārikās*, there are some minor problems (Cardona 2017: 412).

Paramalaghumañjusa, *Laghumañjusa* and *Vaiyākaraṇasiddhāntamañjusa*. It appears close to that of Gāgābhṭṭa's *Bhāṭṭacintāmaṇi* and Jagadīśa Bhāṭṭācārya's *Śabdaśakti-prakāśikā*. All in all, it seems to follow also the original arrangement of Kauṇḍabhaṭṭa's *Vaiyākaraṇabhūṣaṇa* which introduces an original organization of semantic and syntactic issues discussing them under section-headings which directly deal with case-endings (*vibhakti*) and cases (*kāraka*). According to Deshpande (1992: 79–80), “it is perhaps possible to trace the inspiration for this new arrangement for discussion of semantics according to morphological categories to Gaṅgeśa's *Tattvacintāmaṇi* and its influence on the subsequent developments in the schools of grammar, Nyāya, and Mimāṃsā”, and, in our specific case, on Khaṇḍadeva's *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya*.

Such an arrangement is significant for the issue at stake, because it anticipates one of the few shortcomings of this new edition detected by Cardona:

Although Ramanuja Tatacharya cites many passages from other works of Mimāṃsā and Nyāya, his very brief introduction does not give the reader an overview of Khaṇḍadeva's relations to other authors of his period and to predecessors with respect to the tenets upheld and argument proposed. (Cardona 2017: 411)⁶

At any rate, it must be said that, in addition to the complexity of the arguments concerning grammar and semantics, although the style of the BTR is apparently terse, it is synthetic, sometimes elliptic, and therefore complex (*śaili ca na sugamā* “not easy to understand”, BTR 2015: iii). For this reason the fresh commentary *Sārāprakāśikā* (hereafter SP) by Tatacharya is definitely most welcome.

In fact, the truly original contribution of this new edition as well as its *quid pluris* is primarily the SP, the final commentary by Tatacharya, a traditional *paṇḍita* well-known among indologists for his long practice of editing Nyāya, Mimāṃsā texts, in composing original commentaries, glosses and elucidations (*vyākhyāna*),⁷ and for writing original independent works (*prakaraṇa*) such as the monumental Sanskrit work *Śābdabodhamimāṃsā*,⁸ as well as for his long-lasting

⁶ For instance, in order to fully access BTR's arguments a synoptic reading of Gadādhara Bhāṭṭācārya's *Vyutpattivāda* (17th cent.) is clearly required, in fact Khaṇḍadeva often refers directly to it. This would facilitate understanding the debate with Nyāya. In fact, the *Vyutpattivāda* can easily be considered the *pūrvapakṣa* (the prima facie view) with respect to several positions of the BTR. Recently, Tatacharya has also commented upon the *Vyutpattivāda* (Tatacharya 2011–2012).

⁷ I would like to mention Tatacharya (1982–1999, 1988, 1995, 1999, 2017) as just a few of several distinct works and commentaries. See also Cardona (2017: 409).

⁸ While glossing the *Dhātvarthanirūpaṇam* section of the BTR, in the SP (p. 195) Tatacharya refers to his *Śābdabodhamimāṃsā* (Tatacharya 2005–2008: IV, 1–55), useful for its meticulous treatment beginning with Maṇḍana Miśra's *Bhāvanāviveka*. Also in the SP's (pp. 414–415) discussion on the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 2.3.19 (*sahayukte 'pradhāne*) there are frequent mentions of the *Śābdabodhamimāṃsā* (Tatacharya 2005–2008: III, 377–412).

collaboration in several *navya-nyāya* translations and explications with Stephen H. Phillips.⁹ Formerly Vice-Chancellor of the Rashtriya Sanskrit Vidyapeetha of Tirupati, *Mahāmahopādhyāya* Professor N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya is one of the greatest living philosophers and authorities in all *śāstras* (Phillips 1995: xi),¹⁰ but specifically in the fields of Nyāya, Vyākaraṇa, Pūrvamīmāṃsā and Uttaramīmāṃsā.

The volume is evidently an important contribution to Indian philosophy of language, in fact it presents several major points, but it displays also a few shortcomings. As Cardona noted on indexes, both the BTR and the SP are full of citations from several works. When these citations concern Pāṇini's *Aṣṭādhyāyī* or Kātyāyana's *Vārttika* they are usually detected and signaled, but all other quotations are either not traced or simply not highlighted. An exact reference to the texts quoted would surely have been a helpful basis for further research, and a relevant tool also from the point of view of contemporary scholarship.¹¹ Nonetheless it should be said that this attitude is typical of traditional scholarship, continuously resorting to the textual heritage but without precisely referring to it. To this point, Cardona said:

I know from having studied with traditional paṇḍitas that some are not overtly concerned with the finer points of tracing quotations.¹² Nevertheless, they are concerned with relations among opposing points of view in their fields and are supremely adept at citing pertinent texts from memory. Ramanuja Tatacharya himself evidences interest in the historical relations among texts when he remarks (p. 467, the last two lines) that all the elaborations on finer points set forth in the text at hand are for the most part found in the *Vyutpattivāda*¹³ but that it is not possible to determine their precise chronology. (Cardona 2017: 412–413)

Of course, the encyclopedic Tatacharya is referring to readers with a textual background analogous to his own; nonetheless, for an average reader it is not easy

9 With Phillips, Tatacharya worked on several editions and translations of *navya-nyāya* texts, such as Phillips and Tatacharya (2002, 2009).

10 N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya is associated with the French Institute of Pondicherry as Honorary Professor and, due to his profound scholarship, he is the recipient of several awards and prizes: the Certificate of Honor for Proficiency in Sanskrit and the Padmabushan title conferred by the President of India, the Chevalier de la Légion d'Honneur by the French government. The Head of the Sri Raghavendra Swamy Matha conferred on him the title of *tarkavācaspati*, while the Sri Vedanta Desika Sampradaya Sabha awarded him the title of *śāstraratnākara*, along with many other recognitions.

11 At p. 113, the BTR quotes Jaimini's *Mīmāṃsāsūtra* and refers to it as 1.1.25, while the SP refers to it as 1.1.24. The correct reference is 1.1.25.

12 For a historical and conceptual survey on the issue, see Freschi (2015: 85–108).

13 For instance, while the BTR (p. 467) interprets two of Pāṇini's *sūtras* – 2.3.28 (*apādāne pañcamī*) and 1.4.24 (*dhruvam āpāye 'pādānam*) – Tatacharya at the beginning of this section of the SP (p. 467) reminds us that all *pariśkāras* of the BTR are usually found in the *Vyutpattivāda* (BTR/SP 2015, 467: *atratyāḥ pariśkārah sarve 'pi prāyaḥ vyutpattivāde dṛśyante | param tu anayoḥ kālavīṣaye nirṇayaḥ kartuṃ na śakyate* |). See Tatacharya (2011–2012).

to figure out what is the entire issue at stake. Just an example among several: at p. 172 in the SP, Tatacharya quotes some works and authors who make extensive use of *navya-nyāya* style and methodology, such as Gadādhara Bhaṭṭācārya's *Caturdaśalakṣaṇī*, and Nāgeśa Bhaṭṭa's *Mañjūṣā* trilogy. On this issue, it would have been much better if a reference page had been given; this service might also have been also quite easy, in fact Tatacharya has commented upon the *Caturdaśalakṣaṇī* (Tatacharya 1999).

In order to read Tatacharya's SP, several advanced notions are required; it must therefore be kept in mind that this gloss is addressed to readers who are definitely well versed in many branches of South Asian philosophy of language. At any rate, Tatacharya never avoids carefully taking the hand of less advanced readers and leading them towards clear comprehension. In fact, one of the major merits of Tatacharya throughout his enormous exegetical endeavor – evident also in the SP – is his continuous attempt at rendering texts manifestly clear as well as useful to all *śāstra*-users.

One of the main features of the pre-modern period is the adherence to the *navya-nyāya* style. Khaṇḍadeva is undoubtedly an author of his own philosophical times, which used *navya* style and methodology profusely (McCrea 2008: 582–583). Besides Khaṇḍadeva's prose itself, this is also witnessed in some remarks by Tatacharya. In fact, as an example, while in the SP he confutes the *naiyāyikas'* opinion concerning the meaning of the seventh-ending (*saptamyārtha*) from the point of view of Khaṇḍadeva (BTR, pp. 589–590; SP, pp. 590–595), he quotes important *navya* works, such as Raghunātha Śīromaṇi's (15th cent.) *Didhiti* and Gadādhara Bhaṭṭācārya's *Gādādhari*. Then, specifically, at p. 590 in the SP, Tatacharya affirms that Khaṇḍadeva writes while keeping in mind Raghunātha's style.

At p. 351 of the BTR, Tatacharya surveys the uses of cases (*kāraḥ*) beginning with the example *bubhuḥṣitam ity atra cādheyatvaṃ dvitīyārthaḥ*¹⁴ in a language strongly *navya-naiyāyika*, but extensively analyzed and clarified. A similar elucidation concerns the meaning of the fifth case-ending (*pañcamyārtha*), where Tatacharya explains the *naiyāyikanavyānām matam* quoted by Khaṇḍadeva (p. 471) with a massive didactical use of *navya* style (pp. 471–472). In these instances of the use of *navya* style, Tatacharya often suggests an elaboration and simplification of the root-text without devaluing the importance of technicalities, but intervening when he judges that the reader might find difficulties.¹⁵

¹⁴ The sentence is quoted entirely at p. 352: *bubhuḥṣitam na pratibhāti kiñcit*. See the SP (p. 315) where we find a kind of general summary – extremely useful from a didactical point of view – on what concerns *karmatva* and *dvitīyārtha*.

¹⁵ Significant are the *navya*-styled discussions in the BTR (pp. 488–489) and SP (pp. 489–490) on the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 1.4.27 (*vāraṇārthānām īpsitaḥ*) and on the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 2.3.50 (*śaṣṭhi śeṣe*) in the BTR (p. 523) and SP (pp. 523–524). The BTR (p. 587) presents also the concept of substratumhood

In the *karmatvasvarūpanirvacana* section of the *dvitīyāvibhaktiyarthavicāraḥ* of the BTR (p. 288) there is a sophisticated discussion on the “epistemic qualifier of verbal cognition in the instance of accusative ending” (*dvitīyāntasthale śābdabodhaprakāraḥ*). In this context we see an instance of the expressive felicity and hermeneutic force of the SP (pp. 288–290) where the argument involves the positions of the *tārkikas* and Khaṇḍadeva, deepening and widening the latter’s position in *navya* style.

Here in a scheme the words of Khaṇḍadeva and SP’s elucidation:

Then Khaṇḍadeva and, consequently, the SP continues to elaborate on the meaning of the second ending. Of course, this passage of the BTR is quite elliptical and therefore requires a great quantity of notions to be properly understood, which cannot be dealt with here. Nevertheless, the SP is quite successful in disclosing the text (see the tables at pp. 8–9):

BTR (p. 288)

*na caivam tattatkarmatvānām bhedaḥ
dvitīyāyāś śaktigrahānuppattiḥ, lāgha-
vena vṛttitve, abhāve ca dvitīyāyāś śak-
teḥ, padārthāntarāṇām
anyalabhyatvena tatra śaktikalpanāyām
gauravāt |*

Furthermore, there is no untenability in ascertaining the meaning of the second case-ending from the difference of various grammatical objects, because due to brevity the primary meaning of the second case-ending rests in occurrence and absence and, [on the other hand] since other meanings of words are available through other [means], on that

SP (p. 288)

*nānu tattatkriyāvvyaktibhedena karmatvānām bhe-
dāṅgīkāre kriyāṇām ānantyāt tatprayuktakarmatvā-
nām cānantatvāt asarvajñasya karmatveṣu
śaktigrahaḥ katham sambhaved iti Śaṅkate – na cai-
vam iti | evam = pūrvarītyā | samādhate – lāghave-
netyādinā | parasamavetakriyājanyaphalaśālītvam
karmatvam | tatra vṛttitvam paratvam (bhedaś ca)
ghaṭake | tayoh dvitīyāyāś śaktiḥ | anyāni kriyā-
nyatvaphalāni anyalabhyāni | kriyā phalam ca
dhātvarthaḥ | janyatvam saṃsargamaryādālabhyam |
avaśiṣṭe vṛttitve (ādheyatve) abhāve ca dvitīyāyāś
śaktiḥ |*

Then [in the words] *na caivam* “and thus there is no...” it is thus doubted: when a difference among the grammatical objects is accepted because of the difference among various individual activities, then unlimited activities take place and countless grammatical objects are determined by them [= those activities]. Thus, how will the ascertainment of the primary meaning concerning those grammatical objects by a non-omniscient individual be possible? [The

(*adhikaraṇatvanirukti*) according to the opinion of certain thinkers (*keśamcin matenādhikaraṇatvaniruktiḥ*), where the definition of *adhikaraṇatva* (*tadbhinnatve sati tatpatanapratibandhakasamyogavan mūrtatvam patanavannirūpitādhikaraṇatvam*) is discussed in the SP (p. 588).

(continued)

BTR (p. 288)	SP (p. 288)
issue there is a cumbrousness in the conceptual construction of the primary meaning.	word] <i>evam</i> [means] “in the previous way”. [Then Khaṇḍadeva] finds a solution, by means of the words starting with <i>lāghavena</i> “due to brevity”. The grammatical object is to be connected with a result produced by an action inherent in others. There [in the definition, the terms] occurrence and alterity (and difference) are both components; in both there is the primary meaning of the second case-ending. Other results produced by action are available through other [means]. The action and the result are the meaning of the verbal root. The property of being produced is being obtainable by means of relational appropriateness (<i>saṃsargamaryādā</i>). The primary meaning of the second-ending rests in the remaining occurrence (in the substratumhood) and in the absence.

BTR/SP (p. 288): *cānantatvāt asarvajñasya* > corrige *cānantatvād asarvajñasya*. On some translations of the enigmatic concept of *saṃsargamaryādā*, see Iwasaki (2016: 60).

In its final part (BTR, p. 288 and SP, p. 289), the discussion focuses on the absence and becomes even more technical when the place of constant absence (*atyantābhāva*) is taken by mutual absence (*anyonyābhāva*) also known as “difference” (*bheda*).¹⁶ In any case this is just one example of the fruitful exegetical activity of Tatacharya.

Another of the several thought-provoking portions of the volume (pp. 486–487) concerns a specific syntactic use of the ablative case (*apādāna*),¹⁷ described by the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 1.4.25 (*bhītrārthānām bhayahetuḥ*).¹⁸ The BTR explains the *sūtra* (p. 486) and the SP (pp. 486–487) elaborates it. Specifically, in the second part of his gloss, Tatacharya examines a portion of verse 1.1.4cd of Vālmiki’s *Rāmāyaṇa* (*kasya bibhyati devās ca jāta-roṣasya saṃyuge*), which Khaṇḍadeva seems not to have explicitly taken into account.¹⁹ The verse is usually read as “Who, when his fury is aroused in battle, is feared even by the gods?” (Goldman 1984: 121), and the SP points out that the genitive of the interrogative pronoun *kasya* is constructed

¹⁶ On the verbal cognition concerning the classical example of the *anyonyābhāva*, see the BTR (p. 395) and the SP (pp. 395–396).

¹⁷ On the considerations on *apādāna* of the SP at p. 482, see Cardona (2017: 412).

¹⁸ “This rule assigns the term *apadana* to the source of fear (*bhayahetu*) when roots having the signification of *bhī* and *trā* are in use” (Sharma 1990: 523).

¹⁹ The hint to this discussion is detected by Tatacharya in the expression *adhikaraṇāvivaḥśāyām* (BTR, p. 486).

BTR (p. 288)

athā hi – grāmam gacchati ity atra dvitīyārtho vṛtītvam dhātvar-thatāvachedake samyoge 'nveti | tajjanakanṇ gamanaṇ dhātvar-tha eva | evaṃ dvitīyārtho 'bhāvo 'pi pratiyogitāsambandhena dhātvartha eva | grāmādīs ca prakṛtyartha dvividhe 'pi dvitīyārthe | evaṃ ca grāmāniṣṭhābhāvapratiyogi grāmavṛttisamyogajana-ka-gamanānukūlakṛtimān ityādīḥ śābdabodhaḥ |

SP (pp. 288–289)

tathā hi – Caitro grāmam gacchati ity atra grāmapadottaradivitiyāyāḥ ādheyatvam, abhāvas cārthaḥ | tatrobhayatra prakṛtyarthisya anvayaḥ | ādheyatve prakṛtyar-thasya grāmasya nirūpītatvasambandhena, abhāve ādheyatvasambandhena anvayaḥ | samyogāvaccchinnavyāpārah gam-dhātvarthaḥ tadghaṭakasamyoge dvitīyārthasya vṛttitvāsyā āśrayatvasambandhena anvayaḥ | dvitīyārthasya abhāvāśrayatvasambandhena dhātvarthavyāpāre 'nvayaḥ | dhātvarthasya ākhyātārthakṛtāv anukūlatvasambandhenānvayaḥ | kṛteḥ prathamāntārthe āśrayatvasambandhena anvayaḥ | tathā ca grāmavṛtyabhāvapratiyogi yaḥ grā-mavṛttisamyogajana-ko vyāpārah tadanukūlakṛtimāṃś caitraḥ iti bodhaḥ iti bhāvaḥ | dvividhe 'pi vṛttitve abhāve cety arthaḥ | ayaṃ tārkikarīyā bodhaḥ | svamate tu grāmavṛttisamyogajana-kagrāmavṛtyabhāvapratiyogivyāpārānukūlā bhāvaneti bodhaḥ | abhāvāḥ atyantābhāvaḥ |

Therefore, in fact, in this instance “He goes to the village” the meaning of the second-ending is occurrence, constructed with the contact which is the delimiter of the property of being the meaning of the verbal root; and the movement generating it is indeed the meaning of the verbal root. In the same way, the meaning of the second ending is also absence, which is indeed the meaning of the verbal root by the relation of counter-positiveness; furthermore, the village, etc. is the meaning of the base. Thus, both of them are the meanings of the second ending. Hence, the verbal cognition results [as such]: the counter-positive [namely Caitra] of the absence residing in the village is endowed with a volitional effort conducing to going, which produces a contact occurring in the village.

Therefore, in fact, in this [example] “Caitra goes to the village” the meaning of the second ending, which comes immediately after the word *grāma-* (“village”) is superstratumhood and absence. There, in both cases, the construction is with the meaning of the base. In the case of superstratumhood the construction concerns – through the relation of determinateness – the village which is the meaning of the base, [while] in the case of absence [the construction] is through the relation of counter-positiveness. The meaning of the root *gam* (“to go”) is an operation delimited by the contact, and the construction of the meaning of the second ending – which is occurrence – rests in the relation of substratumhood in the contact, which is its component. [In addition,] the construction of the meaning of the second ending – which is absence – is in the operation which is the meaning of the verbal root by the relation of counter-positiveness. The construction of the meaning of the verbal root is in the volitional effort of the verb by the relation of being conducing. The construction of the volitional effort is in the meaning of the first ending by the relation of substratumhood. Hence, the [verbal] cognition is as such: the counter-positive of the absence occurring in the village, which is the operation

(continued)

BTR (p. 288)

SP (pp. 288–289)

generating the contact occurring in the village is Caitra, who is endowed with the volitional effort leading to it [namely the operation generating the contact occurring in the village]. This is the idea. The meaning of *dvividhe 'pi* (“both of them”) is [both] occurrence and absence. Such a [verbal] cognition is [explained] through the style of Logicians, while according to my [= Khaṇḍadeva’s] own position the [verbal] cognition is a “bringing into being” leading to an operation whose counter-positive is the absence occurring in the village, which produces a contact occurring in the [same] village. The absence [meanṭ] is a constant absence.

BTR/SP (p. 288): *vṛttivam dhāvarthatāvachedaīke* > corrige *vṛttivam dhāvarthatāvachedaīke*. BTR/SP (p. 288): *grāmapadottaradvitīyāḥ ādheyatvam* > corrige *grāmapadottaradvitīyāḥ ādheyatvam*. BTR/SP (p. 288): *tadanukūlakṛttimāṃś caitraḥ iti bodhaḥ iti* > corrige *tadanukūlakṛttimāṃś caitra itī bodha itī*. On the translation of the Mimāṃsā technical terms *bhāvanā*, see Ollett (2013).

with *saṃyuge* and not with *bibhyati*; otherwise we would have to cope with the incorrectness and inapplicability of *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 1.4.25. Here is the relevant passage:

nanu 'kasya bibhyati devās ca jātaroṣasya saṃyuge' ity atra bhayārthakadhātuyogasadbhāvāt kiṃśabdasottaram apādānārthakapañcamyāṃ kasmāt²⁰ bibhyati ity eva prayogaḥ sādhuḥ | kasyeti ṣaṣṭhyantaprayogasya kathaṃ sādhutvam ity āśaṅkya tatra ṣaṣṭhyantasya kiṃśabdasya na bibhyatinā anvayaḥ | api tu saṃyuge²¹ ity anenānvayaḥ | kasya saṃyuge yuddhe devāḥ bibhyatīty anvayaḥ | atra ṣaṣṭhyarthaḥ saṃbandhaḥ saṃyugānvayī | arthāt saṃyuga-ghaṭitaḥ saṃbandhaḥ ṣaṣṭhyarthaḥ²² bhāvanāyām anveti | kiṃsaṃbandhiyuddhādharakabhayāśrayā devāḥ²³ iti bodhaḥ | na ca kiṃpadārthasya bhayaṃ prati apādānatvābhāve 'pi, saṃyugasya bhayaṃ prati apādānatvavivakṣāyāṃ saṃyugapadottaram pañcamī syād iti vācyam | apādānasamjñāpekṣayā parayā adhikaraṇasamjñāyā apādānasamjñāyāḥ bādhāt²⁴ na pañcamī | adhikaraṇatvavivakṣāyāṃ tu saṃyugapadottaram apādānapañcamī bhavaty eva | vivakṣātaḥ kārakāṇi bhavantīti nyāyāt ...

But in this instance, *kasya bibhyati devās ca jātaroṣasya saṃyuge*, because of the presence of the connection with a verbal root which means fear, after the word *kim* the correct use would have surely been in the fifth ending, which means the ablative case [as such] *kasmāt bibhyati*. How can the use of the sixth-ending *kasya* be correct? Having thus expressed such a doubt on that issue, the construction of the word *kim* in the sixth-ending ought to be with [the verbal form] *bibhyati*; whereas the construction is with this [word] *saṃyuge*. [Thus, this is] the construction “In battle, during war, of whom are the gods afraid?”. In this instance the meaning of the sixth-ending is relation and is constructed with [the word] *saṃyuga*. This means that the meaning of the sixth-ending, which is a relation connected with [the word] *saṃyuga*, is constructed in the “bringing into being”. The gods are the substrata of the fear whose locus is the war, which is connected with [the pronoun] *kim*: this is the [verbal] cognition. Moreover, it cannot be said that – although the meaning of the word *kim* lacks an ablative-nature towards fear, whereas the intention to express an ablative towards fear of the word *saṃyuga* is there – there should not be a fifth-ending after the word *saṃyuga*. In fact, with regard to the technical term of the ablative, [exactly] because of the cancellation of the technical term of the ablative by means of the other technical attribution of the locative, there is no fifth-ending. On the contrary, when there is the intention to express a locative, after the word *saṃyuga* there must surely be the fifth-ending of the ablative, by the [interpretative] maxim “the cases are [attributed] according to the desire of the speaker”²⁵ ...

Although the suggestion of Tatacharya on this issue is correct, from a Pāṇinian grammatical point of view another solution might be sought: to consider the genitive absolute construction in the sense of a mere relation without any specific connotation (*saṃbandhamātra*) as suggested by the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* 2.3.50 (*ṣaṣṭhī*

20 BTR/SP (p. 487): *kasmāt bibhyati* > corrige > *kasmād bibhyati*.

21 BTR/SP (p. 487): *saṃyuge ity* > corrige > *saṃyuga ity*.

22 BTR/SP (p. 487): *ṣaṣṭhyarthaḥ bhāvanāyām* > corrige > *ṣaṣṭhyartha bhāvanāyām*.

23 BTR/SP (p. 487): *devāḥ iti* > corrige > *devā iti*.

24 BTR/SP (p. 487): *apādānasamjñāyāḥ bādhāt na* > corrige > *apādānasamjñāyā bādhān na*.

25 On the source of this specific meta-rule or interpretative rule (*paribhāṣā*), see Houben (2007–2008: 353) and Kawamura (2018: 22).

śeṣe). In fact, “the genitive case is used in the sense of any kāraka when that kāraka is not to be considered a kāraka” (Abhyankar 1986: 400). Thus, the genitive in the texts would merely be a substitute of the ablative, so as to consequently modify the translation as such: “By whom also gods are made afraid when his fury is aroused in battle”.

Another significant issue proposed by the BTR begins at p. 187, and concerns “the epistemic qualifier for constructing the meaning of the *ātmanepada*” (*ātmanepadārthasyānvayaprakāraḥ*). The very first sentence of the paragraph is: *evam upagrahaviśeṣarūpasyātmnepadāder arthaḥ ...* “Hence the meaning of the *ātmanepada* is a particular form of the diathesis ...”. The first sentence of the SP (p. 187) is *upagraha iti ātmanepadasya अपराम् नामा* “*upagraha* is another name for *ātmanepada*”. This seems to be a somehow misleading sentence, because *upagraha* is a technical term indicating a kind of theory of aspects of the verb, which looks at *parasmaipada* (active voice) and *ātmanepada* (middle voice) not as grammatical concepts, but as labels for two groups of conjugational affixes. Nonetheless, in the *Vārttika ad Aṣṭādhyāyī* 3.2.127 it is clear that the term is precisely used in the sense of *ātmanepada*. Therefore, in order to avoid an inclusion of both the voices – *parasmaipada* and *ātmanepada* – within the expression, Tatacharya carefully specifies that in this context the word *upagraha* means simply *ātmanepada*.²⁶

It is quite evident that in his gloss Tatacharya tries to fill up all the voids of the synthetic style of Khaṇḍadeva, clarifying ambiguous words and interpreting difficult passages in a more analytical way. This is detectable also by the fact that Tatacharya – as is usual in traditional glosses – suggests the correct *vigraha* (analysis) of the majority of the nominal compounds.

It is a known fact that ancient, medieval as well as pre-modern commentaries are more difficult than the texts which they are elucidating. On the contrary, not only in the SP but in all his hermeneutical activity, Tatacharya goes against this tendency. He definitely struggles with the text in order to make it clearer, analyzing synthetic expressions and simplifying ultra-technical idioms. In fact, on several occasions of the SP we find the *praghaṭṭakāśaya* “the purport of the doctrine”, clear and comprehensive elucidations, which elaborate upon what Khaṇḍadeva hints at elliptically (p. 35).

The result of these efforts is that the SP is all the more readable, due to such a generous hermeneutical tendency. Besides glossing the BTR, on several occasions the SP focuses precisely on the problem by means of expanded paraphrases, where

²⁶ In the *Aṣṭādhyāyī* the term *upagraha* does not appear, but – besides the above-mentioned *Vārttika* – it is used in a different sense in the *Kāśikā ad Aṣṭādhyāyī* 6.2.134. See Abhyankar (1986: 83–84) who quotes Helārāja *ad Vākyapadīya* 3.12.1, and Misra (1966: 25).

unclear passages, definitions and debates are elaborated. While commenting upon the BTR, Tatacharya is usually also helpful in specifying who is addressed with the use of pronouns like *tat*, *yat*, etc., mainly used in composition, which might sometimes create hermeneutic embarrassment in the reader.

A shortcoming which should definitely be underlined is the enormous, sometimes annoying quantity of typographical errors and misprints, both in the BTS and in the SP. More precisely, in the first 250 pages there are hundreds of these. Then from p. 277 the typographical errors become less frequent and problematic until p. 472 where they begin again, although not as numerous as in the first half of the book. I believe that a bit of additional care in editing and typing would have been appreciated. I hope that with the next edition of the volume this problem will be remedied.

Moreover, although I cannot confirm it for its inconsistency, it seems to me that the SP sometimes tries to simplify the *saṃdhis* of the BTR. This could be a possible explanation for the great quantity of typographical errors and misprints. In fact, while in the BTR the *saṃdhi* are usually correct, they are not in the SP. In any case, if this hypothesis were correct, it would have been more appropriate to state it clearly and try to be consistent throughout the book. Another related problem is that in the volume *saṃdhis* are sometimes respected though interspersed with commas, while on other occasions they are not, such as at p. 19 *pravṛtṭyasādhyatve, iṣṭasādhanatve ca śaktiḥ* and so on.

Another general problem related to the typographical errors already mentioned concerns the placing of Western punctuation. I would be more careful in doing so, because while in some cases it favours the comprehension of the text, in others it is placed carelessly, with confusing results. One of several examples is at p. 20, where the first comma placed is not only useless but misleading, whereas the second is useful: *madhuviṣasamṣṛktānnabhojane kṛtisādhyatvajñāna, iṣṭasādhanatājñānavayasattve 'pi balavadaniṣṭānanubandhitvajñānābhāvān na pravṛtṭiḥ, tasya balavadaniṣṭamarāṇasādhanatvāt |*.

There are many issues and difficult points cleared up by the outstanding gloss of Tatacharya. I think that scholars should not miss the opportunity to read not only the SP, but should also benefit from the entirety of Tatacharya's untiring exegetical mission. I definitely believe that works of this kind are the material evidence of our need to fully safeguard traditional Sanskrit learning. I do hope that *Mahāmahopādhyāya* N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya will delight us with other works in the future. Nonetheless, I would suggest more care for accuracy on the part of the editors. More attentive editors should work with *paṇḍitas*, who – in turn – should attempt to have some Indological training in order to produce not only doctrinally remarkable glosses, but also carefully edited scientific works beyond reproach.

The time also is right for that, as well, after all.

References

- Abhyankar, Kashinath Vasudev. 1986. *A dictionary of Sanskrit grammar*, 3rd revised edn. Baroda: Oriental Institute.
- Cardona, George. 2017. Review of: The Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya of Khaṇḍadeva with the Sāraprakāśikā commentary by N. S. Ramanuja Tatacharya. *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 137(2). 409–413.
- Deshpande, Madhav M. 1992. *The meaning of nouns. Semantic theory in classical and medieval India. Nāmārtha-nirṇaya of Kauṇḍabhaṭṭa* (Studies in Classical India 13). Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Diaconescu, Bogdan. 2012. *Debating verbal cognition: the theory of the principal qualificand (mukhyaviśeṣya) in classical Indian thought*. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Freschi, Elisa. 2015. The reuse of texts in Indian philosophy: Introduction. *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 43(2–3). 85–103.
- Goldman, Robert. 1984. *The Rāmāyaṇa of Vālmīki: An ancient epic of India*. Introd. and transl. by Robert P. Goldman, vol. 1: Bālakāṇḍa. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Houben, Jan E. M. 2007–2008. Sources et histoire de la tradition Sanskrite. *Annuaire de l'École Pratique des Hautes Études (EPHE). Résumés des conférences et travaux* 140. 352–356.
- Iwasaki, Yochi. 2016. The saṃsarga-maryādā in the Śabdamaṇyāloka of Jayadeva. *Journal of Indian and Buddhist Studies* 64(3). 58–64.
- Kawamura, Yūto. 2018. Candragomin's theory of karman. *Journal of Indian and Buddhist Studies* 66(3). 18–24.
- McCrea, Lawrence. 2008. Playing with the system: Fragmentation and individualization in late pre-colonial Mīmāṃsā. *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 36(5–6). 575–585.
- Misra, Vidya Nivas. 1966. *The descriptive technique of Pāṇini: An introduction* (Janua linguarum: Series practica 18). The Hague & Paris: Mouton & Co.
- Ollett, Andrew. 2013. What is Bhāvanā. *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 41(3). 221–262.
- Phillips, Stephen H. 1995. *Classical Indian metaphysics: refutations of realism and the emergence of "New Logic"*. Chicago: Open Court.
- Phillips, Stephen H. & Navalpakkam S. Ramanuja Tatacharya (eds.). 2002. *Gaṅgeśa on the Upādhi: the "Interferential undercutting condition"*. Introduction, translation and explanation by Stephen H. Phillips and Navalpakkam S. Ramanuja Tatacharya. New Delhi: Indian Council of Philosophical Research.
- Phillips, Stephen H. & Navalpakkam S. Ramanuja Tatacharya (eds.). 2009. *Epistemology of perception. Transliterated text, translation and philosophical commentary of Gaṅgeśa's Tattvacintāmaṇi (Jewel of reflection on the truth). Pratyakṣa-khaṇḍa. The Perception chapter*, 2nd edn. New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass.
- Subrahmanya Sastri, Anantakrishna (ed.). 1970. *Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya by Khaṇḍadeva*. Banaras: Sanskrit Maha Vidyalaya – Banaras Hindu University.
- Sūryanārāyaṇa Śāstrī, Peri (ed.). 1985. *Khaṇḍadeva Bhāvaprakāśaḥ: Mahāmahopādhyāya Khaṇḍadevaviracitasya Bhāṭṭarahasyasya vyākhyā* [Khaṇḍadeva Bhāvaprakāśaḥ: A commentary on the Bhāṭṭatantrarahasya written by the Mahāmahopādhyāya Khaṇḍadeva]. Rajahmundry: Prāpisthānam V. Gopalakrishna Sastry.
- Sharma, Rama Nath (tr.). 1990. *The Aṣṭādhyāyī of Pāṇini*, vol. II. Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal.
- Ramanuja Tatacharya, Navalpakkam S. (ed.). 1988. *Gaṅgeśopādhyāyaviracitā pakṣatā raghunāthaśiromaṇikṛtayā dīdhityā gādhādharaḥhaṭṭacāryakṛtayā dīdhitiprakāśikayā ḍā. en. es. rāmanujatātācāryakṛtayā dīdhitiprakāśikāvākhyayā bālabodhinyā ca sahitā*

